

EFFECT OF DIETARY SUPPLEMENTATION OF BROWN SEAWEED (*Turbinaria conoides*) and red seaweed (*Gracilaria salicornia*) MEAL WITH YEAST (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) ON CARCASS TRAIT, GUT HEALTH, BLOOD BIOCHEMICAL, IMMUNITY AND SHELF LIFEY C Bawane¹, V K Munde², S M Wankhede³, S A Amrutkar⁴, S N Rindhe⁵, M G Nikam⁶, P M Kekan⁷, K K Khose⁸ And N M Karad⁹

College of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Parbhani, Maharashtra 431 402

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Abstract

An experiment was conducted to evaluate the impact of diet supplementation of brown seaweed (*Turbinaria conoides*) and red seaweed (*Gracilaria salicornia*) meal with yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) on performance of broiler chicken. Broilers (240) were divided into 4 treatment groups. In the S_0 standard broiler diet (BIS- 2007), S_1 standard broiler diet with 1% (*Turbinaria conoides*) with Yeast, S_2 standard broiler diet with 1% (*Gracilaria salicornia*) with Yeast and S_3 standard broiler diet with 0.5% (*Gracilaria salicornia*) and 0.5% (*Turbinaria conoides*) with Yeast treatment groups respectively, per 100 kg of feed. The results revealed that the carcass weights for S_0 , S_1 , S_2 , and S_3 were weighed at 1681g, 1804g, 1879 g, and 1858g. live weight rise was considerably higher in S_3 than that of other treatment group ($P < 0.01$). *E. coli* count was statistically significant different ($P < 0.01$) showed a numerical decrease in *E. coli* count in S_3 compared to the other treatment group. Total viable count and *Lactobacillus* count was not differing statistically significant amongst the experimental groups. Increased in Villus length and crypt depth in S_3 compared to the other treatment group. there was not statistically significant variations in the blood levels of AST, ALT, LDL, and triglycerides across the experimental groups. But the level of HDL numerically increased in S_3 . There was no statistically significant impact on the weight of Thymus, Relative weight of Thymus and HI anti RD Titre. However, there was statistically significant increase in weight of bursa and Relative weight of bursa ($P < 0.05$) was observed in S_3 and S_2 in comparison to S_1 and S_0 groups. The TBA levels on the third and sixth day were found to be statistically not significantly different ($P > 0.05$). As compared to S_0 , S_1 , and S_2 groups, it was observed that the water holding capacity % (WHC), CP%, and fat % exhibited higher values in S_3 group.

Keywords: *Turbinaria conoides*, *Gracilaria salicornia*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*,

Introduction

India's poultry industry has flourished significantly over the past several decades, effectively transforming from traditional home farming to a thriving agri-based sector (Panda *et al.*, 2016). Poultry is effective at turning feed into high-value products in a very short amount of time. The protein shortage that plagues many nations is starting to be significantly alleviated by eggs and chicken meat (Michalak *et al.*, 2020). In order to replace animal proteins, soybean meal, and maize in feed, people are interested in examining alternate feed supplies. Consumption of marine foods is growing popularity as people become more aware of the importance of nutrition and health (Granato *et al.*, 2020).

As a source of proteins, lipids, polysaccharides, minerals, vitamins, and enzymes, they are regarded as the most significant dietary supplement of the twenty-first century. Algae are a good source of pigments like chlorophyll and water and fat soluble vitamins. Microalgae, also known as tiny algae, are single-celled, photosynthetic organisms that may flourish in both fresh and saline water. They have a long history of use as a human diet because they are a rich source of nutrients and physiologically active substances, such as protein, amino acids, n-3 long chain polyunsaturated fatty acids, microelements, vitamins, antioxidants, and carotenoids (Thapa, 2020).

The use of seaweeds in chicken feeding is now gaining attention. When seaweeds are included in feed, which are a rich source of bioactive components, poultry performance and health can be increased (Michalak *et al.*, 2020). Seaweeds have a significant amount of minerals because they can absorb inorganic substances from the environment (Lemessa, 2022).

Over the past ten years, interest in feeding seaweed to livestock has grown (Buschmann *et al.*, 2017). One of the richest sources of natural antioxidants and antimicrobials among marine species is seaweed. The majority of red seaweeds include water-soluble vitamins B and C, including amine and riboflavin, as well as liposoluble vitamins such carotenoids (as provitamins of vitamin A). Along with chlorophyll, the carotenoids are several pigments that collectively provide the colour of seaweed. They are also potent antioxidants. (Morais, *et al.*, 2020).

The biggest seaweed is brown algae (*Turbinaria conoids*), which has received more exploitation for animal food than any other form of algae. Compared to other meals, brown seaweed has a high

concentration of the minerals iodine (I) and calcium (Ca) (Yengkhom *et al.*, 2019).

The genus *Gracilaria* is an economically significant group of seaweeds because numerous species are used to make agar, which is used in medications, human meals, and poultry feed (Vinuganesh *et al.*, 2022). In most *Gracilaria* species, the protein content ranges from 7% to 13%. The proportion of total amino acids (AA) in the red seaweed *G. salicornia* that contained sulphur was 8.7%. The amount of total amino acids in the *G. salicornia* (889.78 mg g⁻¹ protein d.w.) was substantially higher (Tabarsa *et al.*, 2012). Probiotics can be used in place of antibiotics to boost the broilers' immune system and growth performance. *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* enhances digestion and intestinal villi length, it is one of the greatest alternatives and additives for chicken feed for increasing production performance (Kumar *et al.*, 2019). It is abundant in vitamin B complex, selenium and chromium-containing trace elements, as well as crude protein with a high biological value (40–45%) (Celik *et al.*, 2001).

Prebiotics content of both Seaweeds and addition of Yeast will perform function of synbiotics. The synbiotics are combinations of prebiotics and probiotics that may work together to benefit the gastrointestinal tract's healthy microbiota (Tayeri *et al.*, 2018). The promotion of probiotic bacteria' survival in the gastrointestinal system is the main goal of that kind of combination. Synbiotics were developed to address potential issues with the survival of probiotics in the digestive system. Probiotics operate as a barrier to protect the gastrointestinal tract and have a positive impact on intestinal homeostasis. Prebiotics, on the other hand, provide probiotic microorganisms with energy and nutrition (Markowiak and Śliżewska 2018). Hence, the current research trial has been designed to evaluate the inclusion of yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) with red seaweed (*Gracilaria salicornia*) and brown seaweed (*Turbinaria conoides*) meal on performance of broiler.

Materials And Methods

The research work was approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee and the Board of Studies. The study was conducted on 240 day-old commercial broiler chicks of the *VenCobb 430Y* strain at the Experimental Broiler Shed, College of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Parbhani (MAFSU, Nagpur) for a period of 6 weeks. Randomly, One-day-old, 240 broiler chickens were grouped into four experimental groups, S_0 , S_1 , S_2 and S_3 each of which had four repetitions of 15 birds. The groups were created using a completely

randomized method. In the S₀ standard broiler diet (BIS- 2007), S₁ standard broiler diet with 1% (*Turbinaria conoides*) with Yeast, S₂ standard broiler diet with 1% (*Gracilaria salicornia*) with Yeast and S₃ standard broiler diet with 0.5% (*Gracilaria salicornia*) and 0.5% (*Turbinaria conoides*) with Yeast treatment groups respectively, per 100 kg of feed. Broiler chicken efficiency was determined by traits such as Carcass, Gut Health, Blood biochemical, Immunity and Shelf life.

Manual evisceration was carried out to determine carcass traits. On day 42, two birds from each replicate (8 birds per treatment) were selected randomly and slaughtered to determine intestinal weight, intestinal length, duodenum thickness, intestinal pH and microbial count of each bird. By subsequent opening of carcasses of birds, the entire gastrointestinal tract was removed aseptically. The Total viable count (TVC) was determined by using plate count agar asper method described in Bacteriological Analytical Manual (1998). At the time of sacrifice thymus and bursa of sacrificed bird were collected, weighed accurately and weights were recorded.

In the present study meat samples of one bird per replicate of each treatment were stored at 4°C in LDPE (low density polyethylene) bags and their oxidative stability. TBA value was determined according to the method described by Strange et al (1977) with slight modification. 15 gm of meat sample from gastrocnemius and peroneus longus muscle was minced and transferred to centrifuge

tube. 22ml of 0.6M sodium chloride solution was added in that and centrifugation was done at 3500 rpm for 15 minutes. Supernatant (V) was measured for calculating the WHC. At the end of sixth week, blood samples of one bird from each replicate were collected. For blood biochemical.

Statistical analyses: The data collected during the experiment were subjected to statistical analyses as per Completely Randomized Design (CRD) method with treatment as factor following statistical procedure of Snedecor and Cochran (1994). Means were compared as per Duncan's multiple range test and data were processed for statistical analyses using SPSS Software package (26.0).

Results And Discussion

Carcass trait

The live body weights of birds selected for slaughtered were statistically significant, in S₁, S₂ and S₃ compared control S₀. live weight rise was considerably higher in S₃ than that of other treatment group (P<0.01). Group S₀ was the control group with the lowest live weight, while groups S₁, S₂, and S₃ were the treatment groups with the greatest live weight of broiler chickens, respectively, based on numbers. There was statistically significant (P<0.05) impacts on carcass properties of the chickens in group S₁, S₂ and S₃ compare to S₀. The carcass weights for S₀, S₁, S₂, and S₃ were weighed at 1681g, 1804g, 1879 g, and 1858g, respectively.

Table no 1. Carcass traits of broiler chicken

Parameters	Treatment				SEM	P-Value
	S ₀	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃		
Live Wt (g)	2347 ^a ± 20.29	2488 ^b ± 39.12	2562 ^b ± 15.72	2512 ^b ± 29.35	24.00	0.001
Carcass Wt (g)	1681 ^a ± 23.77	1804 ^b ± 25.82	1879 ^b ± 37.76	1858 ^b ± 40.97	24.75	0.005
Dressing %	71.59± 0.415	72.54± 0.649	73.36± 1.563	74.01± 2.230	0.675	0.659
Edible meat Wt (g)	1500 ^a ± 10.86	1639 ^b ± 16.67	1734 ^c ± 22.77	1735 ^c ± 44.66	27.63	0.001
Edible Meat %	63.90 ^a ± 0.412	65.91 ^b ± 0.640	67.71 ^b ± 1.073	69.15 ^b ± 2.421	0.799	0.091
Giblet Wt (g)	112.3± 1.182	120.5± 4.401	121.0± 1.764	122.0± 2.221	1.564	0.086
Giblet %	4.786± 0.083	4.842± 0.134	4.725± 0.084	4.858± 0.096	0.047	0.788
**Means bearing different superscripts 'a' and 'b' in a row differ significantly(P<0.01) *Means bearing different superscripts 'a' and 'b' in a row differ significantly (P<0.05)						

Considering the results of the current investigation on carcass weight, Khalilnia *et al.*, (2023), Both experimental treatments had no significant effects on carcass yield, internal organs, or the pH of the meat from the thighs and breasts (p > 0.05) fed a diet supplemented with probiotics and *Spirulina platensis* microalgae powder. El-naga *et al.*, (2018) investigated the effects of adding brown algae to drinking water. They found that, after five weeks, dietary treatments had no deferable effect on the relative weight of the carcass features under study (81.30 vs. 79.99).

The addition of *Turbinaria murayana* seaweed to broiler chicken feed did not significantly affect the carcass percentage (P>0.05), according to Reski *et al.*, (2021).

There was numerical increase in dressing percentage compared to the control group. Groups S₁, S₂ and S₀ had the lower dressing percentages as compared to group S₃ having numerically the higher. Abudabos *et al.*, (2015) reported that the proportion of green seaweed *Ulva lactuca* at levels of 0%, 1.0%, and 3.0% had a significant impact on dressing percentage (P<0.004); birds with 3.0% seaweed had a greater dressing percentage than other birds. However, there was not a significant difference in the percentage of birds dressed between the groups that received 0% and 1.0% seaweed. The study conducted by Toghyani *et al.*, (2011) revealed that birds fed a meal enriched with

manan-oligosaccharides (1.78%) did not exhibit any significant effect of the supplements on dressing percentage.

The proportion of giblet weights in the treatment groups (S₁, S₂, and S₃) did not differ statistically (P>0.05) from the giblet weights in the control group S₀. In sequence, the giblet weight displayed a numerical increase in the S₃, S₂, and S₁ groups compared to the S₀ group.

According to Chavan *et al.*, (2022), diets supplemented with 0.1 and 0.13% brown seaweed had greater giblet weights. Oliveira *et al.*, 2023 diets with increasing levels of seaweed bran giblet showed no significant difference (P > 0.05). Seaweed supplementation improved and increased relative organ weights, according to Balasubramanian *et al.*, (2021)

The edible meat weight of experimental birds differed significantly (P<0.01) among treatment groups in comparison to the control group (S₀), however, S₃ group edible meat weight was statistically and numerically greater than that of the other groups. Based on experimental data, the edible meat percentages of broiler chicks in treatment groups S₁, S₂ and S₃ were comparable to each other and substantially greater than those control S₀.

Internal organs of the carcass were not substantially impacted by any of the experimental treatments, according to Khalilnia *et al.*, (2023) (p > 0.05). Tang *et al.*, (2017) discovered for all dietary treatment

groups, there were not any significant differences in the relative weights of the liver and heart.

Gut Health

E. coli count was statistically significant different ($P < 0.01$) showed a numerical decrease in *E. coli* count in S_3 compared to the other treatment group. Total viable count and *Lactobacillus* count was not differing statistically significant amongst the experimental groups. However, there were numerical decrease in bacterial count in all treatment groups (S_1 , S_2 , and S_3) compared to the control group (S_0). Khalilnia *et al.*, (2023), observed that when broilers were given *Spirulina platensis* microalgae together with a native probiotic, there was a significant difference increase in *Lactobacillus* bacteria observed with a significant reduction in *Escherichia coli* population ($p < 0.05$) respectively. Bai *et al.*, (2019) found that on days 21 and 42, the addition of *Laminaria japonica* powder (LJP) (1-3%) to the broiler chicken diet together with 300 mg or 600 mg of cecropin/kg

resulted in a substantial reduction in *E. Coli* levels ($p < 0.05$). However, the addition of 1-3% LJP to the diet did not resulted in a significant rise in *Lactobacillus* counts ($p > 0.05$). Choi *et al.*, (2016) observed that when pig fed was provided alone with probiotics, *Ecklonia cava*, or both, the amount of *Lactobacillus* spp. in the cecum rose ($p < 0.01$) and the amount of *E. coli* reduced ($p < 0.05$) in both supplements.

Mookiah *et al.*, (2014) found that at 21 days old, the caecal populations of *lactobacilli* and *bifidobacteria* were significantly ($P < 0.05$) increased as compared to control group, whereas the caecal *Escherichia coli* was significantly ($P < 0.05$) decreased, when probiotics, prebiotics, or synbiotics were supplemented as compared to control group. The caecal bacterial load was observed to be considerably reduced ($p < 0.05$) when 0.1 or 0.13% of brown seaweed was added to the diet, according to Chavan *et al.*, (2022).

Table no 2. Gut health of broiler chicken

Parameters	Treatment				SEM	P-Value
	S0	S1	S2	S3		
<i>E. coli</i> count (log cfu/gm)	1.120 ^a ±0.040	0.938 ^{ab} ±0.033	0.800 ^b ±0.032	0.858 ^c ±0.035	0.035	0.001
Total viable count (log cfu/gm)	6.335±0.165	6.298±0.195	6.053±0.271	6.048±0.257	0.107	0.712
<i>Lactobacillus</i> count (log cfu/gm)	19.13±0.410	18.83±0.634	18.80±0.578	19.35±0.372	0.236	0.853
Villi height(µm)	752.1 ^a ±28.14	933.2 ^b ±40.73	923.8 ^b ±29.00	985.9 ^b ±22.78	26.57	0.001
Crypt depth(µm)	169.5 ^a ±8.490	203.5 ^b ±8.855	203.8 ^b ±7.499	203.0 ^b ±9.513	5.408	0.038
Villi height/crypt depth	4.497±0.413	4.608±0.253	4.543±0.146	4.872±0.117	0.122	0.743

*Means bearing different superscripts 'a' and 'b' in a row differ significantly ($P < 0.05$)

The prebiotic components present in seaweed and probiotic yeast exhibit a synbiotic effect by increasing the abundance of beneficial bacteria in the gastrointestinal tract. Upon reaching the colon, the prebiotic is selectively fermented by specific members of the native microflora. This stimulation of bacterial growth further leads to the synthesis of bacteriocins, which play a role in suppressing the proliferation of harmful bacteria across all experimental groups.

Villus length and crypt depth were statistically differed significantly ($P < 0.01$) and showed increase in Villus length and crypt depth in S_3 compared to the other treatment group. Followed by treatment group S_2 , S_1 and S_0 Villus length and crypt depth increases, also there were numerically increase in length and depth in all treatment groups (S_1 , S_2 , and S_3) compared to the control group (S_0)

Blood biochemical parameters

The results for total protein, albumin, globulin, and albumin:globulin ratio did not show a statistically significant variance between the experimental groups, according to the data presented in table 3 From the data it was observed that there was not statistically significant difference regarding total protein, albumin, and globulin levels and A:G ratios of the all-experimental groups. However, total protein and globulin values of the S_2 group were found numerically higher than the all other experimental groups.

However, total protein and globulin values of the S_2 group were found numerically higher than the all other experimental groups. In the present study there was not statistically significant variations in the

Table no. 3 Blood biochemical parameters of broiler chicken

Parameter	Treatment				SEM	P- Value
	S ₀	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃		
Total protein (g/dl)	3.698± 0.055	3.768± 0.064	3.828± 0.142	3.773±0.055	0.041	0.773
Albumin (g/dl)	1.38± 0.044	1.473±0.061	1.438± 0.045	1.418±0.036	0.023	0.587
Globulin (g/dl)	2.35± 0.047	2.295±0.026	2.39± 0.116	2.355±0.056	0.032	0.814

blood levels of AST, ALT, LDL, and triglycerides across the experimental groups. But the level of HDL numerically increased in S_3 . In contrast to the control group (S_0), the treatment groups (S_1 , S_2 , and S_3) had similar values for LDL and triglycerides and higher values for HDL.

The current study's findings indicate that ALT and AST readings were numerically lower in the treatment groups, while it was higher in the control group S_0 . On the other hand, these numbers did not vary significantly. The information included under the criteria of serum biochemistry suggests that there hasn't been any negative impact on the levels of serum biochemicals, such as total proteins, albumins, globulins, and HDL.

Shokaiyan *et al.*, (2019) found Triglyceride levels in the blood were significantly ($P < 0.05$) decreased when fucoxanthin and probiotics were used instead of antibiotics. According to Munde *et al.*, (2018), the treatment group that received formulations containing 1.5% seaweed byproducts had the highest serum concentration of total protein, whereas the control group's concentration was lower ($P < 0.001$) than that of the other groups. Serum globulin concentration was lower ($P < 0.001$) in the control group than in the other groups, but there was no difference between the other groups. Treatment diets did not ($P > 0.05$) affect plasma albumin, according to research by Mohammadigheisar *et al.*, (2020). However, there was a trend ($P = 0.06$) for a quadratic rise in globulins when birds were given 10 g/kg seaweed.

A:G ratio	0.588± 0.020	0.642±0.027	0.605± 0.026	0.603±0.024	0.012	0.484
ALT	43.50± 1.708	43.00±0.913	44.00± 1.291	43.29±1.404	0.615	0.961
AST	65.50± 1.041	65.00±1.080	65.25± 1.109	64.75±2.287	0.712	0.592
Triglycerides (mg/dl)	146.75± 1.65	144.0± 1.47	142.75± 0.853	141.2±2.71	0.960	0.226
LDL (mg/dl)	64.00± 1.471	59.25± 2.926	58.75± 2.32	56.00± 1.870	1.238	0.135
HDL (mg/dl)	110± 5.017	114.5±3.797	117± 3.109	118.8±3.172	1.920	0.437

Tang et al., (2017) Supplemented hens with prebiotic, probiotic, or synbiotic reduced ($P < 0.05$) the levels of blood total cholesterol, low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol, alkaline phosphatase (ALP), and alanine aminotransferase (ALT) at 36 and 52 weeks of age. Supplementation resulted in a reduced heterophil to lymphocyte (H/L) ratio at 36 and 52 weeks of age by increasing ($P < 0.05$) lymphocyte percentage and decreasing ($P < 0.05$) heterophil percentage.

Contrary to the results of the present study, Balasubramanian et al., (2021) found that treatment groups given red seaweed meal had substantially different albumin levels.

Table no.4 Immunological parameters of broiler chicken

Parameter	Treatment				SEM	P- Value
	S ₀	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃		
Weight of Thymus (g)	7.910± 0.367	8.347± 0.264	8.305± 0.237	8.404± 0.273	0.139	0.626
Relative weight of Thymus	0.328± 0.016	0.335± 0.006	0.324±0.011	0.335± 0.011	0.005	0.886
Weight of bursa (g)	1.322 ^a ± 0.039	1.273 ^a ± 0.029	1.425 ^b ±0.021	1.500 ^b ± 0.008	0.026	0.001
Relative weight of bursa	0.055 ^a ± 0.002	0.051 ^a ± 0.002	0.056 ^{ab} ±0.001	0.060 ^b ± 0.001	0.001	0.010
HI anti RD Titre	5.886± 0.134	5.958± 0.109	5.855±0.255	6.018± 0.285	0.095	0.946

**Means bearing different superscripts 'a', 'b' and 'c' in a row differ significantly ($P < 0.01$)
*Means bearing different superscripts 'a' and 'b' in a row differ significantly ($P < 0.05$)

According to Martinez *et al.*, (2019), feeding red algae powder to the diet raised ($p < 0.05$) the relative weights of the thymus and the bursa of Fabricius. The lymphoid organs' relative weight increased in proportion to the spleen's weight. Serum IgG, IgM, and IgA were shown to be elevated ($p < 0.05$) in the *Ecklonia cava* groups of pigs fed a diet supplemented with probiotics, *Ecklonia cava*, or both. Probiotics and *Ecklonia cava* had a significant interaction for IgG at the second phase as well.

Bai et al. (2019) noted that the supplementation of broiler dietary supplements with *Laminaria japonica* powder at a level of 300 mg/kg cecropin resulted in enhancements to the immune system. This

Table no. 5 Shelf life of meat of broiler chicken

Parameters	Treatment				SEM	P-Value	
	S ₀	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃			
TBA (mg/malonaldehyde/kg)	0 day	0.097 ^a ±0.004	0.087 ^{ab} ±0.003	0.092 ^b ±0.005	0.079 ^b ±0.003	0.002	0.027
	3 days	0.815±0.032	0.788±0.035	0.745±0.023	0.723±0.033	0.017	0.201
	6 days	1.253±0.137	1.088±0.046	1.128±0.042	1.045±0.035	0.040	0.308
WHC	71.41±1.043	74.85±1.763	72.74±0.768	74.00±1.408	0.672	0.309	
CP %	19.13±0.410	19.43±0.567	20.89±0.487	20.25±0.412	0.277	0.082	
Fat %	3.008±0.142	3.463±0.165	3.200±0.147	3.633±0.162	0.093	0.061	

*Means bearing different superscripts 'a' and 'b' in a row differ significantly ($P < 0.05$)

Qadri *et al.*, (2019) observed a significant ($P < 0.05$) improvement in water holding capacity (WHC) and fat when diets with 1.50 and 1.25% *Kappaphycus alvarezii* were fed to treatment groups in comparison to controls. On the other hand, meat's 2-thiobarbituric acid reactive substance activity increased ($P < 0.05$). According to research by Nhlane *et al.*, (2020), adding green seaweed meal to the diet for the remaining seven days of room temperature storage resulted in similar ($P > 0.05$) improvements in shelf life markers compared to the control diet. Khalilnia *et al.*, (2023) studied that *Spirulina platensis* microalgae was compared with a native probiotic. The findings reveal that the birds' meat shelf life indicators improved.

Immunological parameters

There was no statistically significant impact on the weight of Thymus, Relative weight of Thymus and HI anti RD Titre. However, there was statistically significant increase in weight of bursa and Relative weight of bursa ($P < 0.05$) was observed in S₃ and S₂ in comparison to S₁ and S₀ groups. Wherever, there had numerical difference in treatment group S₁, S₂, S₃ weight of Thymus compared to control S₀. There was a positive response for all immunological measures in group S₃, which was followed by S₂ and S₁.

supplementation also led to an increase in the spleen and thymus indexes on day 21, as well as in the bursa of Fabricius index on day 42 ($p < 0.05$). However, the bursa of Fabricius index on day 21 and the spleen index and thymus index on day 42 ($p > 0.05$) were unaffected.

Shelf life

The group S₀ was statistically significantly higher TBA (thiobarbituric acid) levels on day 0 than in S₁, S₂, and S₃ groups. The TBA levels on the third and sixth day were found to be statistically not significantly different ($P > 0.05$). As compared to S₀, S₁, and S₂ groups, it was observed that the water holding capacity % (WHC), CP%, and fat % exhibited higher values in S₃ group.

Brown (*Turbinaria conoides*) and Red (*Gracilaria salicornia*) seaweed meal (50:50 ratio) at the rate 1.0kg/100kg of feed along with Yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) 50 gm/100 kg in broiler chicken feed, considerably increased the weight of the carcass, the weight of edible meat, the dressing percentage, the percentage of edible meat, villus height and the meat's shelf life.

Brown (*Turbinaria conoides*) and Red (*Gracilaria salicornia*) seaweed meal (50:50 ratio) at the rate 1.0kg/100kg of feed along with Yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) 50 gm/100 kg in broiler chicken feed improved immunity and decreased mortality rate in treatment groups.

Acknowledgment

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